

THE ROLE OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS IN PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT

Egamberdiev Oyatillokh Alisher ogli¹,
Tojimamatov Jamshidbek Iqboljon O'g'li²
Student of Fergana State University
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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the role of physical culture and physical education in the full development of the individual, the issue of educating the younger generation in a comprehensive and harmonious way.

The level of culture of a society is largely determined by the degree of development, disclosure and use of individual human abilities. It is especially important to emphasize that in the system of universal cultural values, one of the main components is the level of health and physical fitness of the entire population at different age periods and especially in the first half of life, which determines the possibilities of mastering all other values. Physical culture and sports are an independent type of human activity, the significance of which in the development of society is very diverse. They have a definite impact on social production, on the formation of a person as a person, on the development of social relations.

Physical culture is part of the general culture of society, aimed at strengthening and improving the level of health. It

performs a social function - the upbringing of a comprehensively and harmoniously developed personality.

At present, the understanding of physical culture as a social and individual value has increased, which makes it possible to form new trends in the development of public opinion and personal motivations for mastering the values of physical culture by everyone.

Physical culture and sports play an important role in personality formation. Many social situations are played out in sports activities, which allows an athlete to gain life experience for himself, to build a special system of values and attitudes.

The process of development of culture consists in the fact that a person simultaneously creates and creates culture, objectifying his own essential forces in it, and forms himself as a social being,

mastering, de-objectifying the previous culture. And to reduce this whole process only to purely “spiritual” activity, to ignore aspects of physical culture, its physical development and upbringing means not only impoverishing the process itself, but also giving an incorrect interpretation of its essence.

Physical culture is part of the general culture of society, one of the spheres of social activity aimed at strengthening health, developing the physical abilities of a person and using them in accordance with the needs of social practice.

This is a special and independent area of culture. It arose and developed simultaneously with the general culture of man. Physical culture can be viewed as a specific response to the needs of society for physical activity and a way to meet these needs.

In the personal aspect, it represents that part of the general culture of a person, which is an internal measure of the degree of development of physical forces and motor skills, as well as the level of life and vitality of a person and his state of health. It allows using its specific means and methods to reveal the potential of a person. Physical culture is a unity of real (practical) and ideal (mental) activity. In the process of this activity, a person enters into connections and relationships with the social and natural environment. The more universal his connections are, the more comprehensively and harmoniously a person will be developed, the more universal his connections with the environment will be.

The functions of physical culture can be divided into 4 groups:

1. General development and strengthening of the body (formation and development of physical qualities and abilities, improvement of motor skills, health promotion, counteraction and containment of involution processes, etc.).
 2. Preparation for labor activity and defense of the Motherland (increasing efficiency, resistance against unfavorable working conditions, physical inactivity, vocational training, etc.).
 3. Satisfaction of the needs for active rest and rational use of non-working time (entertainment, games, compensation).
 4. Disclosure of volitional, physical qualities and motor abilities of a person at extreme levels.
 5. For normal functioning, a person needs a certain amount of physical and social components, such as food, air, sunlight, rest, movement, etc. Physical and mental activity, normal functioning of abilities are possible in a limited range of conditions.
- In society, physical education is the most important means of educating a new person, harmoniously combining spiritual wealth, moral purity and physical perfection. It helps to increase the social and labor activity of people, the economic efficiency of production. The physical culture movement is based on the multilateral activities of the state and public organization in the field of physical culture and sports (FCS). At the present stage, the task of transforming the mass physical culture movement into a nationwide one, based on a scientifically grounded system of physical education, which covers all strata of society, is being solved. Existing state systems of program and assessment standards for physical

development and preparedness of various age groups of the population.

Compulsory physical education classes according to state programs are carried out in preschool institutions, in all types of educational institutions, the army, at enterprises, etc. - during the working day (industrial gymnastics, physical culture breaks, etc.). For the organization of mass physical culture and health-improving work at enterprises, institutions, educational institutions, etc., collectives of physical culture have been created.

The main tasks of physical education of the younger generation are: health promotion and hardening of the body, proper physical development, providing children and youth with the necessary motor skills and abilities, improving their physical abilities, promoting the formation of the most important moral and volitional qualities.

Physical education is one of the constituent parts of the education system, which has the goal of strengthening human health and its correct physical development. In unity with mental education, moral and aesthetic, labor education and training, physical education contributes to the all-round development of a person's personality.

The program provides for training sessions in the amount of three hours a week, including one hour of optional. In addition,

it is envisaged to carry out health-improving activities in the daily routine (morning exercises, physical culture breaks, etc.), mass physical culture and sports work outside the classroom (sports sections, general physical training groups, sports competitions and recreational activities, health days, classes in a sports and health camp). The program recommends an approximate thematic plan of physical education classes with the definition of the types of activities (theory, practice), sports (gymnastics, athletics, ski training, swimming, tourism and sports games) and the calculation of hours by year of study. The content of topics on the theory of physical education is given, as well as the amount of knowledge and skills that students must master, mastering the technique of sports.

Thus, the role of physical culture in the formation of basic qualities and personality traits is very great. A person must be able to think abstractly, develop general provisions and act in accordance with these provisions. But it is not enough just to be able to reason and draw conclusions - it is necessary to be able to apply them in life, to achieve the intended goal, overcoming the obstacles encountered on the way. This can only be achieved with the right physical education.

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